

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH AND CREATIVE ABILITIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

An important feature of building a lesson in primary school is its saturation with various forms of work. The lesson should consist of several carefully thought-out parts, united by a common theme and goals, but involving different forms of learning activities. For example, in a literary lesson, children play words together with the teacher, compete in the correctness and speed of completing the task, make riddles to each other and the teacher and guess them, look for the missing words.

Key words: Elementary education, skills, game methods.

At the same time, a complex educational problem is solved - children learn to conduct a sound analysis of words, that this is done using various methods and accurately on the basis of a pre-thought-out organization and implementation by children of various types of educational tasks.

The teacher's explanations, even when using a variety of visual material, do not give the desired result in teaching children if they are not combined with the practical activities of the students themselves.

Exercises that contribute to the development of creative abilities of younger students in literary reading lessons have their own special system. The system refers to the sequential inclusion of creative tasks from simple to complex. Creativity requires will, the ability to overcome one's laziness and objective difficulties, activity in all matters and, first of all, in knowledge, self-expression of individuality, the personality of the student through creativity.

Methodological techniques that ensure the implementation of the method of creative reading: expressive reading, connected reading, creative tasks, posing an educational problem in the lesson.

In the primary grades, the development of expressive reading is of great importance, since expressiveness based on a thoughtful analysis of the text contributes to a deep understanding of the work, its main themes, and also contributes to the development of creative reading. In order for students to read expressively, they need to be helped in choosing and using means of artistic expression and means of sound expression (voice, intonation, tempo, pauses, logical stress, expressive/independent reading of the children themselves (by heart or from books) is a kind of report to the teacher, the class, to oneself about their understanding of the text, its interpretation. Such work can be carried out in the form of a competition of readers. For example, intonation, tempo about opening, expressive reading of folktales/fables attention in the lessons is paid to folktales, especially work with proverbs, riddles, folk tales. Working on riddles is an exercise in the independent development of thinking, ingenuity, and imagination. They teach children to speak vividly, figuratively, simply. Lessons using riddles are interesting and do not tire students, giving them useful exercises for the mind. Composing a riddle, children get the opportunity to concentrate their attention on a specific, actually perceived or invented subject in the imagination.

The game is the main activity of the child. It plays an important role in the formation and development of the mental, emotional, physical and creative abilities of the child. The game helps to develop memory, thinking, imagination, attention, helps to form the phonemic perception of the word, activates mental activity, attention, stimulates speech. As a result, children become interested in the lesson. Not to mention the fact that didactic games contribute to the formation of spelling/grammar of the younger student. In an effort to take into account the age characteristics of young schoolchildren when teaching, teachers often unjustifiably get carried away with the game in the lesson. You need to know that not every game and not always in an effective form of learning. The game method of teaching is not a game in the proper sense of the word. This is giving a game form to a task that has cognitive content by introducing one or more elements of the game into it. Each element can be a game plot, rules, attitudes to win as a result of the implementation of certain rules and the achievement of a given goal. Examples of didactic games: Didactic game: "In a word." Students are invited to replace combinations of words and sentences with one word that has the syllables: cha, sha, zha, zha, zha. 1. Fairy tales - ... (Hans) 1.2. A vessel with a handle and a spout for boiling water or brewing tea - ... (Spoon) 3. Group of a fox - ... (Hole). Didactic game: "On the way around." Purpose: to fix the spelling of words with the combination: - dir. Teacher invites children to replace the phrases of the noun + noun type proposed by them with another one so that one of the words includes the combination: - dir in its composition. The form of a fairy tale - ... is fairy tale here) fairer apples - ... (apple (and What's fine - ... (what fine)) etc. With the help of the plot, a playful form can be given to both the story and conversation, and organization of practical activities of children.

The introduction of rules means that the children themselves turn into "travelers", "drivers", "architects", etc. They can also depict inanimate objects, for example, the student creates the "rule" of a certain sound and takes his place in the word or, playing the role of a certain number, looks for his "neighbors" - adjacent numbers. The characters solve purely educational problems, but the game situation creates a long-term emotional background and makes it possible for children to transfer them from involuntary to voluntary action without noticing.

Being in win most often takes the form of competition in the tasks "Who is faster?", "Who is more?", "Who is more accurate?" etc. This may concern, for example, the naming of objects with given characteristics (selection of words with a given sound, numbers corresponding to one or another condition). Winning children are rewarded with clips, badges, that is, their work is evaluated, although they do not receive marks. In working with six-year-old students, the teacher's habitual idea that visual material for lessons should be bright, catchy, detailed. It turned out that for a six-year-old student, visual teaching aids are the better, the more accurately they reflect the characteristic qualities and properties of the objects that are being studied at the moment. To do this, the teacher uses a variety of learning tasks. For example, logical tasks. Their value is that their solution takes place in a specific activity that is interesting for the child (drawing, designing, modeling). In the greatest extent taking into account the peculiarities of thinking of children of this age, its visual-effective nature. In conclusion, I would like to dwell on the reconstruction of A. Ginzburg, which serves to develop the creative abilities of students - try to establish a teaching plan that is fully consistent with the needs of your students - the teacher must study and determine the real possibilities of students; - plan the purpose of the lesson as an interconnected set of tasks of education, upbringing and student development; - choose the best combination of teaching methods; - provide the most favorable, hygienic, moral, psychological and material conditions for learning; - analyze the creativity interest in every child, teach to work, help to understand and find oneself, which will be a product of integration.

Literature

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Summary

This article reflects the development of speech and thinking in primary school students